

Power line following based on measurements of the magnetic field

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Abstract—In this paper, we present a method to control the UAV to follow the power line with a specific position and orientation based only on the measurement of the magnetic field generated by the current flow in the power line. The measurements from four magnetometers attached to the UAV are used to solve an optimization problem that involves determining the relative pose of the UAV with respect to the power line. Based on the relative pose, the UAV is controlled to follow the power line in a predefined position and orientation. Experiments in a test setup have confirmed that the method is applicable in a realistic environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every year, millions of kilometers of power lines around the globe have to be checked regularly. In many countries, this is done by ground personnel or sometimes by helicopters. In recent years, more and more unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have been used to inspect power lines, but they are still mainly controlled manually by pilots.

Currently, different methods of automatic inspection of power lines with UAVs are used, mostly by setting waypoints as in [1], where the authors used several heterogeneous UAVs for inspection. In this methods, the UAV follows pre-programmed GNSS waypoints, which must be known in advance.

For automatic inspection when the coordinates of the power line are not known, a method for following the power line is required. Various methods for tracking power lines are presented in the literature. Most of these methods are based on optical sensors such as LIDARs and cameras. Such examples are shown in [2], [3], [4], [5] and [6]. A slightly different concept is presented in [7], where the authors present a method based on radar measurement.

Since high-voltage power lines usually carry large currents that generate a magnetic field around the line, in this paper we focus on the following power lines based on the measurements of the magnetic field with magnetometers.

In our previous papers [8] and [9] it is shown that unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) can be localized by the magnetic field of two long parallel power lines using magnetometer measurements. The papers presents an analytical and numerical solution to the localization problem. Furthermore, in [10] we have shown a method for grasping conductors with a robotic arm carrying alternating current based on the measurement of two magnetometers.

Fig. 1: Concept of UAV flying next to the operational power line based on measurement of magnetic field

There are several systems that rely on the magnetic field for localization and navigation. Most of the work is designed for indoor environments with special infrastructure for magnetic navigation. Such an approach is shown in [11] and [12] for vehicle navigation, which follows a wire that conducts alternating current laid under the floor based on two components of the magnetic field. This type of navigation is available in commercial autonomous guided vehicles. A similar approach is presented in [13], where the magnetic guidance band is placed on the floor for localization, which is detected by a magnetic flux sensor.

In [14] a positioning system for inductive charging of electric vehicles was developed. For this purpose, at least two magnetometers are mounted on the underbody of the vehicle to sense the low-frequency magnetic field emitted by the charging coil in the parking lot. The vehicle then locates the charging coil by applying the trilateration principle to the measured data [15]. Since the magnetization effects in the ferromagnetic underbody can be compensated [16],[17], the assistance system achieves millimeter accuracy.

The number of works deals with localization based on the geomagnetic field maps of the environment. Examples of such work are [18], [19], [20], [21], [22] and [23].

The real experiments with the drone touching 15-kV power lines are shown in [24], together with the presentation of the magnetometer readings.

In [25], the authors present the reconstruction of overhead line parameters for inspection by drones, with experiments performed in the laboratory without a drone.

In [26] the authors present a concept in which an aircraft is attached to the power line based on magnetic field measurements. In [27], the authors present a patent in which the autonomous flight of the aircraft for inspection is considered

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based on magnetic field and electric field measurement.

In this paper, we present a method for autonomous following of the power line with the UAV based on the measurement of the magnetic field with four magnetometers (see Figure 1). With the presented method, we can define desired position and orientation of the UAV with respect to the power line and move along the line.

In section II the magnetic localization method used in the work is presented, in section III the method for controlling the UAV based on magnetic localization is described and in section IV the experimental setup used in the experiments is presented. Section V shows the results of the experiments, and the conclusion is presented in VI.

II. MAGNETIC LOCALIZATION

Based on our previous work presented in [9] and [10], we adjusted the numerical magnetic localization method based on the optimization of the criterion function that computes the magnetometer measurements based on the expected positions of the line. The optimization parameters are the expected positions of the line, while the error value is the difference between the actual measurements and the expected measurements.

A. Numerical method for magnetic localization

The current flowing through the conductor generates in vacuum a magnetic field with strength:

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2\pi r} \quad (1)$$

where B is the strength of the magnetic field, I the current flowing through the conductor, r the distance from the conductor and μ_0 is the permeability of the vacuum:

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi 10^{-7} \text{ H/m} \quad (2)$$

The equation (1) provides strength of the magnetic field at some distance r from the conductor and its direction is defined by the right hand rule in a way that it is always circumferential to the isomagnetic lines. In this way, on location of each magnetometer mounted on the UAV, magnetic field is a 3-dimensional vector.

Figure 2 shows the coordinate frames used for magnetic localization. Since the power line generates a magnetic field that is the same for every y in the coordinate system of the power line (direction of the line), magnetic localization can only be used for localization in the x and z directions, which are perpendicular to the direction of the power line.

The yaw orientation ψ of the UAV with respect to the power line is calculated in the same way as presented in [9] and [8].

For the location of the power line, the numerical method optimizes the location of the UAV in the coordinate frame of the power line so that the measurement of the magnetometers transformed into the coordinate frame of the power line \mathbf{B}_{mi} best correspond to the magnetic field that would be generated at their location $\mathbf{B}_i(x, z)$. For 4 magnetometers, numerical localization is performed by minimizing the following criteria:

Fig. 2: Coordinate frames used for localization. The red arrow represents the x direction, the green arrow represents the y direction, and the blue arrow represents the z direction.

$$J(x, z) = \sum_{i=1}^4 |\mathbf{B}_{mi} - \mathbf{B}_i(x, z)| \quad (3)$$

where $J(x, z)$ is a criterion that depends on the variables x and z , which define the location of the UAV in the coordinate frame of the power line.

Further details about optimization can be found in [9].

If all magnetometers are in the same plane, magnetic localization provides two solutions, one on each side of the power line. By knowing the approach side to the power line, this limitation can easily be circumvented. By adding additional magnetometer that is not in the same plane as the others, this problem is completely solved.

B. Processing the measurements of the alternating magnetic field

Since power lines carry an alternating current, the magnetic field is also alternating, which means that the measurements must first be processed before they can be used for localization. For this purpose, the amplitude (A), phase offset (ϕ) and direct current (D) components of the signal are determined so that the alternating magnetic field can be described as follows:

$$B_{alt}(t) = D + A \cos(2\pi ft + \phi) \quad (4)$$

where B_{alt} is the magnetic field, f is the signal frequency (usually 50 or 60 Hz) and t is the time.

In our previous work [9], we presented optimization based method for extracting A , ϕ and D from the signal. The optimization criteria used is:

$$J_{alternating}(A, D, \phi) = \sum_{i=1}^N (m_i - B_{alt}(i\delta_t))^2 \quad (5)$$

where $J_{alternating}(A, D, \phi)$ is the optimization criterion, m_i is the i -th of N samples used for processing, and δ_t is the sampling time. The optimization is performed using the Nelder-Mead optimization algorithm, which is run twice

for two different initial parameter sets (A_0, D_0, ϕ_0) for optimization.

The same optimization procedure is repeated for all 4 magnetometers used for each of the axes x , y and z . If the phases of two axes match, they have the same direction, if their phases are apart by π radians, they have opposite direction. For this, all measurements must be synchronized.

III. MAGNETIC FIELD BASED UAV CONTROL

For the control of UAVs, the localization of the UAV must generally provide 4 values, the location x , y , z and the yaw orientation ψ . From the local coordinate frame of the power line, the magnetic localization presented in section II provides information about x_{pl}^{uav} , z_{pl}^{uav} and ψ (\mathbf{P}_M). As mentioned above, magnetic localization does not provide information about the distance along the power line (coordinate y_{pl}^{uav}). To successfully control the UAV, we provide a control strategy intended for the outdoor UAV platform with GNSS and altitude sensor controlled in position mode.

The control goal of the UAV is to follow the line while maintaining the relative pose to the power line, i.e. to keep x_{pl}^{uav} , z_{pl}^{uav} and ψ at the previously defined reference values x_r , z_r and ψ_r (\mathbf{P}_{Mr}), which were defined in advance, e.g. with the desired view of the camera.

Based on GNSS and the altitude sensor, the UAV autopilot provides information in the global coordinate frame \mathbf{C}_g , which is defined by $\mathbf{P}_C(x_{ap}, y_{ap}, z_{ap}, \psi_{ap})$ which is obtained by fusing the information from GPS, IMU and altitude sensor. The UAV is controlled in the position mode of the fused result. Since the UAV is controlled in position mode, the control algorithm must provide the reference pose in the global coordinate frame \mathbf{C}_g , which is defined by $\mathbf{P}_r(x_{apr}, y_{apr}, z_{apr}, \psi_{apr})$.

The challenge in controlling the UAV based on the magnetic field is to calculate \mathbf{P}_r for each time instance for a given current pose \mathbf{P}_C and magnetic pose \mathbf{P}_M so that the UAV first moves in the direction of the desired pose \mathbf{P}_{Mr} and then along the line over the desired distance.

To control the pose of the UAV to \mathbf{P}_{Mr} with known pose \mathbf{P}_M , which increases the accuracy by approaching the power line, we propose to set the following reference position in each time instance k :

$$\begin{aligned} x_{apr}(k) &= x_{apr}(k-1) - g_p[(x_r - x_{pl}^{uav}) \cos(\psi_{ap}) - \\ &\quad - (y_r - 0) \sin(\psi_{ap})] \\ y_{apr}(k) &= y_{apr}(k-1) - g_p[(x_r - x_{pl}^{uav}) \sin(\psi_{ap}) + \\ &\quad + (y_r - 0) \cos(\psi_{ap})] \\ z_{apr}(k) &= z_{apr}(k-1) - g_p(z_r - z_{pl}^{uav}) \\ \psi_{apr}(k) &= \psi_{apr}(k-1) - g_o(\psi_r - \psi_{ap}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where y_r is the reference in the y -direction of the power line, which has the value 0 when approaching the set point, g_p is the position gain and g_o is the orientation gain, which must be less than or equal to 1. In this way, the system moves in the direction of the desired pose. During this time, the speed of the system is limited.

When the system comes close to the target set point defined by (6), y_r of the reference changes so that it becomes K_y instead of 0. So when the UAV assumes the desired position and orientation, it begins to move along the power line. Since the power line setup is relatively short, K_y changes its sign when it travels a certain distance along the power line. In this way, the left-right movement along the power line is achieved.

It is considered that the system has reached the desired set point when the following condition is met:

$$|P_{Mr} - P_M| < \begin{bmatrix} \Delta_x \\ \Delta_y \\ \Delta_z \\ \Delta_\psi \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where Δ_x , Δ_y , Δ_z and Δ_ψ are allowed tolerances for x , y , z directions and UAV orientation ψ .

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

An experimental setup for testing power line following consists of a power line with a conductor carrying alternating current and a UAV equipped with four magnetometers.

A. Power line setup

The setup consists of a line carrying alternating current with a frequency of 50 Hz. The power source is a transformer with a rated input voltage of 230 V and a rated output voltage of 36 V at a rated power of 2.5 kW. To enable various configurations of the power line that may occur in reality, we prepared a setup with 3 such transformers mounted on the cart, together with distribution systems and 6 places for 2.5 kW 1-ohm resistors. The cart with transformers and resistors can be seen in Figure 3. With this type of setup, we can create power line configurations with one conductor, two conductors of the same phase, three conductors with three different phases and 6 conductors where each pair of conductors carry one phase. For the experiments in this paper, we only use one conductor with one phase and one return line, which supplies a constant alternating current of 64A RMS.

The wires are laid at a height of 2 m with a length of about 12 m. The wires used are 25mm² HO1N2-D insulated wires. The return line is located on the ground at a distance of 5 m from the setup wire and further away from the flight area. The schematic of the top view of the power line setup is shown in Figure 4.

B. Magnetometers

LIS3MDL 3-axis magnetometers are used for magnetic localization. These sensors measure the magnetic field strength in a range from ± 4 gauss to ± 16 gauss and provides output via the SPI interface. Communication with a sampling rate of 1000 Hz was achieved for all four sensors with the Teensy 4.1 board. The data collected by the Teensy is transferred to the on-board computer via the USB port. The magnetometers are attached to the UAV as shown in the Figure 5, with a distance of 47 cm between the two magnetometer pairs. The

Fig. 3: Cart with transformers and resistors

Fig. 4: Schematic of the top view of the power line setup

positions of the magnetometers were chosen so that they are as far away as possible from power cables and motors, but also cover the largest polygon.

C. UAV

The UAV used is a Fly4Future T650 UAV with 4 T-motors MN4116 Navigator KV170. The autopilot used is Pixhawk and the on-board computer is Intel Nuc. During the experiments. The control framework used is the "Multi-robot Systems Group (MRS) UAV system" [28] described in [29] running on Linux Ubuntu 20.04 with the Noetic distribution Robot Operating System (ROS). In addition to the MRS for UAV control, an additional framework for magnetic localization is implemented.

V. RESULTS

A flight test was carried out with the setup presented in section IV.

The UAV was launched near the power line, where it took off. When it was in the air, the magnetic control was started

Fig. 5: Location of magnetometers on UAV

Fig. 6: Position response from autopilot position estimation

and at that moment it began to move towards the desired set point. When it reached the set point, it moved about 2 meters along the line in one direction. After 2 meters, it changed direction and began to move in the opposite direction along the power line. The movement continued for several cycles.

Figure 6 shows the position of the UAV in the global frame provided by the autopilot, while Figure 7 shows the position based on the magnetic field in relation to the power line and the reference location. From the responses in the global frame, it can be seen that the UAV moves left-right while maintaining its altitude. The responses for magnetic localization show that the UAV maintains its position and orientation in relation to the power line at the reference setpoint.

Fig. 7: Magnetic field localization of the UAV and control references

Fig. 8: Path of the UAV and location of the power line setup shown on Google Earth photo

Figure 8 shows the flight path of the UAV and the location of the power line setup in Google Earth [30], while Figure 9 show the flight path of the UAV and its orientation during movement. It can be seen from the figures that the UAV moves consistently parallel to the power line while maintaining the orientation of the UAV to the power line.

Figure 10 shows the responses of magnetometer 1 during the experiment (top image) and the processed magnetic field vector (bottom image) during the flight. The figure shows that the magnetometer measurements maintain their values after the drone has reached the desired set point and started moving along the line. The video of experiments is presented

Fig. 9: Path of the UAV (blue) and orientation of the UAV (red arrows) in global frame

in the attachment of the paper and on YouTube. The video of experiments is presented in the attachment of the paper and on YouTube on <https://youtu.be/RUv7FdGkvs>.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented a method for controlling UAV that makes it possible to follow the power line. The method is based on the measurement of the magnetic field generated by the operational power line setup. The method was tested in an outdoor experiment in which the UAV was equipped with four magnetometers and followed the power line in the desired position and orientation. The experiments have shown that the UAV successfully adopts the desired position and orientation in relation to the power line, but also that it successfully follows the power line. The results are promising and could enable autonomous flight based on magnetic field-based localization in the vicinity of the real power line.

Future work includes flying along the 3-phase system with 3 or 6 conductors and implementing a visual obstacle avoidance strategy to avoid obstacles that may occur when following the real power line.

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Fig. 10: Raw measurements of Magnetometer 1 for all 3 axes and determined amplitude and direction (processed raw measurements) of the magnetic field components for Magnetometer 1 during the flight

Fig. 11: Images of UAV flying next to the power line setup with highlighted power location and UAV location (in red)

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